
Mesenchymal stem cells strategies in cancer immunotherapy

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Abstract: Mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) have been a new research focus for cancer treatment. Future cancer sufferers will considerably profit from their use in the future. Tumor-directed migratory and integration capacities of MSCs are exceptional, making them potential carriers for the delivery of anticancer medicines, notably cytokines. Their usage in the clinic has lasted around 10 years. The use of mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) to create successful cancer treatments has been demonstrated in everything from animal models to human studies.

1. Introduction

Cancer is a general term for a group of disorders defined by uncontrolled aberrant cell development with a high proclivity for invading healthy bodily tissues (1). Cancer remains a serious obstacle on a global scale (2). According to the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), by 2030, there will be 13.1 million cancer-related deaths each year (3). In many cases, traditional treatment, such as surgical resections with adjuvant radio-chemotherapy, has failed. The inadequacy of anticancer medicines to effectively treat malignancies is due in part to their inability to target the tumor, long-term resistance, and systemic or local damage (4). Novel techniques are needed to overcome the present limitations of commonly used cancer medicines. Immunotherapy is a new cancer treatment strategy that uses the body's own immune system and its components to kill cancer cells in a biocompatible and targeted manner with few side effects. Although the immune system as a whole is generally incapable of counteracting cancer cell strategies (5), cancer immunotherapy provides a number of techniques to aid in tumor reduction and eradication. Immunotherapy has emerged as a critical method for raising our arsenal in the fight against cancer to unprecedented heights. Attempts to use immunologic modifications to stop tumor development may be split into two categories: passive and aggressive. By targeting a distinct collection of autologous cellular antigens known as tumor-associated antigens (TAAs), active immunotherapies use the immune system to mediate cancer regression (6). Passive immunotherapy uses noninvasive techniques to give immunological materials, such as monoclonal antibodies, cells, or cell-derived products, to tumor-bearing hosts in the hopes of enhancing current anti-tumor responses and aiding the immune system's battle against cancer (7).

2. Approaches to cancer immunotherapy in a nutshell

Cancer vaccines, monoclonal antibodies (mAbs), cell therapy, and non-specific cancer immunotherapies with adjuvants are the four primary functional approaches used in cancer immunotherapy. Targeted cancer medicines, such as mAbs, are now one of the most common therapy alternatives. Finding the proper cancer cure is not always straightforward, and mAbs have been shown to be more effective against some malignancies (8). Over the last two decades, the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has authorized more than a dozen

antibody treatments for cancer treatment (9). Rituximab was the first anti-cancer antibody to be authorized, and it is used to treat patients with B-cell non-lymphoma. Hodgkin's Trastuzumab (anti-HER2 antibody for breast cancer) and Gemtuzumab ozogamicin (anti-CD33 antibody for acute myeloid leukemia) were approved at the same time (10). Ibritumomab tiuxetan, a radiolabeled anti-CD20 mAb authorized in 2002 to treat Non-lymphoma, Hodgkin's and cetuximab, a chimeric anti-EGFR antibody used to treat head and neck and colorectal cancer, are two further examples of therapeutic antibodies (11).

Because of their strong specific binding capacity for a broad spectrum of chemicals, antibodies have been described as innovative anti-cancer treatments (12). Their capacity to deliver target-specific inhibition and immune-mediated elimination of malignant tissue over traditional chemotherapeutic drugs reveals a considerable advance in anti-cancer therapeutic techniques (13).

Despite these benefits, significant barriers are now impeding the widespread adoption of therapeutic mAbs. Due to their big size (about 150 kDa), structure, and valency, they have a high monetary cost, a short half-life, poor tissue accessibility, and tumor uptake (12). In general, intravenous injection at large doses results in clinical effectiveness. This might raise the risk of life-threatening consequences, such as allergic responses such as acute anaphylaxis and poisoning (14).

Cell therapy uses autologous immune cells that have been ex vivo grown or modified to provide an anti-neoplastic impact in the fight against cancer (15). In cellular treatment, lymphocytes and dendritic cells (DCs) are frequently utilized (16). DCs are the immune system's most powerful inciting cells, but their capacity to digest and present tumor antigens is critical for generating protective anti-tumor immune responses (5). In tumor immunology, complete DC activation is a challenge since it appears to be performed by pathogen-associated molecules rather than cancer-associated DC activation triggers, illustrating the fact that tumors masquerade as self-tissues to elicit tolerance rather than immunity (17). Because the recruitment of tumor-specific T cells with the goal of generating a cytotoxic response is the holy grail of cancer immunotherapy, adoptive T cell transfer has grown in popularity in recent years (18). Tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes were the ones who started the initial attempts at adoptive cell transfer (TILs). TILs that have been expanded are frequently 'exhausted,' with poor performance and rapid drop-off (19). The field has been resurrected thanks to genetically modified peripheral blood cells. T-cell receptors (TCRs) or chimeric antigen receptors (CARs) for tumor-specific neoantigens may be present in them (20). These T cells have the ability to eradicate tumors. Nevertheless, the inadequate antitumor activity of these cells frequently results in long-term remissions of malignant processes (15). On-target/off-tumor toxicity is a key disadvantage of the TCR approach (21). As a result, adoptive T cell transfer, as a promising technique, must be refined to maximize anti-tumor activity while minimizing side effects.

Non-specific immunotherapies aim to stimulate the immune system in a more broad fashion against malignancies. Cytokines such as interleukins and interferons are non-specific immunotherapy drugs. As previously stated, these immune mediators are not normally found in the bodies of patients who have immune checkpoint inhibitors. Cytokines are pleiotropic regulating proteins that can operate as both systemic or local agents. They have the potential to influence immunological function and inflammation (22). Cytokines are useful in cancer

treatment because they boost anti-tumor immunity, prevent the creation of new tumoral vasculature, and induce death in cancer cells (22).

The use of immune-stimulating cytokines such as interleukin-2 (IL-2) (23, 24), interferon- (IFN-) (25), and interleukin-12 (IL-12) (26) in systemic treatment has resulted in significant dose-limiting toxicities. The use of targeted cytokine immunotherapy to overcome the heterogeneity of malignant cells and tumor cell defense is being investigated (27), with notable reductions in systemic adverse effects. Cell-based approaches, such as employing DCs, fibroblasts, or mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs), aim to mitigate the disadvantages of systemic cytokine delivery. MSCs are multipotent plastic-adhering multipotent cells that may develop into a variety of lineages (28). They were used as "tumor-associated stromal cells" to permanently eradicate invasive malignant cells. Furthermore, compared to immunomodulatory methods based on the production of bioactive chemicals, MSCs carrying transgenes maintain long-term expression (up to 6 months) in vivo (29, 30). They also have a great affinity for injured and inflammatory tissues, including the tumor microenvironment (31, 32). Compared to other cellular delivery vehicles such as autologous tumor cells, fibroblasts, and DCs, MSCs' tumor tropism makes them ideal cellular vehicles for delivering therapeutic proteins precisely to cancer growth areas. This review will explore cancer immunotherapy, with a focus on MSC-mediated cancer gene therapy and the use of cytokines in cancer immunotherapy.

3. In cancer immunotherapy, cytokines play an important role.

Cytokines are molecular messengers produced by the immune system that can encourage the activation of a well-organized, robust, yet self-contained response to a specific antigen.

The name "cytokines" refers to a group of tiny proteins that range in size from 5 to 20 kDa. Interferons (IFNs), ILs, chemokines, lymphokines, and tumor necrosis factor (TNF) are examples of cytokines that are engaged in autocrine signaling pathways that mediate eukaryotic cell interconnections via signaling processes (33). Unlike other immune system communication mechanisms, cytokines have a dispersed effect and can reach far-flung destinations via blood circulation. This allows these molecules to spread complex immunological messages in the shortest amount of time possible (34). Ectopically producing cytokines as a treatment regimen to induce an efficient immune response to inhibit tumor development has great hope. Recent research has focused on cytokine characterisation and the utilization of their vast signaling networks to combat cancer. The same property of completely distinct cytokines might stimulate immunological effector cells and stromal cells in the tumor environment, assisting cytotoxic effector cells in tumor cell detection (35). We present a quick overview of the most often utilized cytokines in the therapy of neoplasia, as well as a significant number of trials that employ acquired immune mediators.

Interleukins

The use of particular cytokines has demonstrated tumor suppression in animal models (36, 37) and has shown promising results in human clinical studies (38). In recent years, clinical studies of cancer patients have looked at a variety of cytokines, including IL-7, IL-4, IL-6, IL-12, IL-15, IL-18, IL-21, and, most notably IL-2 (39).

Interleukin 2 (IL-2) is a kind of immunoglobulin (IL-2).

IL-2, which can produce long-lasting responses in a subgroup of mRCC (metastatic renal cell carcinoma) and metastatic melanoma patients (40, 41), is the finest example of cytokines' promise in cancer immunotherapy. The T cell proliferation factor IL-2 was discovered in

mitogen-stimulated lymphocyte cultures (42). As a master regulator of the G1 to S phase transition in T-lymphocytes, IL-2 regulates the amplification of naive T cells (43, 44), and hence plays a critical role in the immune response induction of cytotoxic T lymphocytes (CTLs) (43, 45). Strong immunostimulatory effectors like IL-2 may trigger enormous immune responses without the need for a particular antigen, using a variety of innate and adaptive immune cell types such as natural killer (NK) cells (46), B cells (47), monocyte/macrophages (48), and neutrophils (49). In 1992, the FDA approved IL-2 for the treatment of renal cell carcinoma, and in 1998, it was approved for the treatment of metastatic melanoma, in which it was found to have an antitumor impact in around 20% of patients (50, 51). The use of systemic IL-2 injection is, however, restricted. This medication was associated with severe systemic toxicity that affected practically all organs, and the IL-2 protein had a short half-life (52). The generation of cytokines locally provides an interesting answer to this problem. Following the early experiments on the insertion of cytokine genes into somatic cells, this method was used. Allogeneic or autologous genetically modified fibroblasts that release IL-2 were injected at the tumor site for this aim. Mammary adenocarcinoma, colon cancer, melanoma, fibrosarcoma, glioma, and leukemia all had excellent results (50-57). In order to abolish tumorigenicity and activate protective immunity in mouse tumor models, cytokine delivery by irradiation of autologous or allogeneic tumor cells might be an acceptable vehicle (55, 58, 59,60). Tumor immunotherapy improves in animal models, according to studies on modified tumor cells that release IL-2 after gene transfer through retroviral vectors (61,62,63,65). Furthermore, tumor growth suppression was achieved by injecting an adenoviral vector producing IL-2 directly into the tumor (66). Various modified autologous tumor cells, including melanoma cells, were generated after encouraging pre-clinical results (67). Because original tumor cultures from each patient have distinct attitudes toward gene transfer, autologous techniques pose significant issues when utilized on a broad scale (68). Due to these limitations, the clinical use of allogeneic tumor cell lines was chosen to produce a stable and well-characterized transgenic expression system. In Phase I and II clinical studies, allogeneic cells that generated IL-2 were tested in patients with various solid and hematological malignancies (69,70,71).

In cancer therapy, several antineoplastic drugs have been suggested to have synergistic effects. In a syngeneic neuroblastoma model, Siapati et al. revealed that IL-2 and IL-12 transfected into human and mouse Neuro-2A cells will likely result in improved anticancer impact of both interleukins (72). The B7 proteins play an important role in T-cell activation as costimulatory molecules produced by antigen-presenting cells (APC) (73). In human melanoma models, studies have shown that vaccination based on B7 protein paired with cytokine-expressing cells, i.e. employing polycistronic retroviral vectors encoding IL-2 and B7-1 genes, has synergistic effects (74).

Interleukin 4 (IL-4) is a kind of immunoglobulin (IL-4).

IL-4, like other major cytokines studied in cancer immunotherapy, exhibits pleiotropic actions on different immune cells (75). Tumor cells that were genetically engineered to produce IL-4 were shown to promote neoplastic lesion rejection and increase tumor infiltration by DCs, resulting in increased TAA cross-presentation (76, 77).

IL-6 (interleukin-6) is a multifunctional cytokine that has potent anticancer effects (78). Transfection of the IL-6 gene inhibited tumor development in a mouse fibrosarcoma model (79). Furthermore, therapeutic immunization with autologous tumor cells expressing IL-6 and

IL-2 prevents tumor growth in a lung metastasis model and results in total melanoma regression in a well-established metastatic mouse melanoma model (80).

Interleukin 7 (IL-7) causes antitumor effects mostly through T-cell involvement (81). This cytokine stimulates CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells while also increasing the activity of lymphokine-activated killer (LAK) cells (82, 83). When transduced into human melanoma cell lines, IL-7 acts as an antineoplastic agent in human colon cancer xenografts and increases immunogenicity (84, 85).

In melanoma and sarcoma animal models, interleukin 12 (IL-12) vaccines containing tumor cells mutated by the IL-12 gene have demonstrated encouraging outcomes (86, 87). It has a strong stimulatory impact on NK and T cells, causing them to produce large quantities of IFN- γ , increase natural cytotoxicity, and contribute to the development of Th1 cells and IL-2-activated B cells (88). In an animal model, a murine sarcoma cell line modified to produce IL-12 using a retroviral vector showed potent anticancer effects. By promoting CD8⁺ T-cell infiltration, increased apoptosis, and disrupting tumor neovascularization, the IL-2/IL-12 combination proved beneficial in overt tumor regression. This evidence backs up the efficacy of IL-12 gene therapy in the treatment of cancer in humans (87).

Interferons (IFNs) are another well-known cytokine used in cancer treatment. IFNs are a protein and glycoprotein family having antiviral, antiproliferative, and immunomodulatory properties (89). IFNs are categorised according to their capacity to bind to certain receptors. Type I IFNs, such as IFN- α and IFN- β , are the most commonly used in the treatment of neoplastic illnesses. They are generated by practically every cell in the body and help a subset of dendritic cells (DC) mature (90, 91). Their production, which is accompanied by an increase in the activity of CTLs, NK cells, and macrophages, has the potential to have catastrophic effects on tumors via immunological stimulation (92, 93). They also force tumor cells to produce MHC class I molecules and have anti-angiogenic and apoptotic effects on tumor cells (94, 95).

Interferon is an antiangiogenic and antimetastatic chemical with a lot of power. It not only stops endothelial cells from growing and migrating, but it also suppresses the production of chemicals involved in angiogenesis and invasion (96). Engrafted gliomas were fully eliminated after tumor cells were transduced using a recombinant adeno-associated virus (rAAV) vector expressing the IFN- γ gene (97). Treatment of highly metastatic PC-3M human prostate cancer cells in nude mice with a recombinant retroviral carrying the murine IFN- γ cDNA inhibited angiogenesis and activated host effector cells, resulting in tumorigenicity reduction of bystander non-transduced prostate cancer cells (98). IFN- γ , like IFN- α , is a complex regulatory cytokine that directs tumor cell death in a caspase-dependent way (99) and inhibits angiogenesis in endothelial cells (100). Glioma cells transfected with an adenoviral IFN- γ (Ad-IFN- γ) vector and given DCs will increase tumor regression by facilitating glioma cell death and presenting glioma antigens, evoking specific immune responses against neoplastic cells (101). In vivo, tumor development is inhibited or abrogated by vaccines containing tumor cells modified with IFN- γ , which is mostly generated by host immune cells (macrophage, T, and NK cells) (102). By increasing the expression of MHC I and II molecules on malignant cells, IFN- γ enhances antitumor immunity (103). IFN- γ can have a detrimental impact on tumor growth by inhibiting angiogenesis by stimulating fibroblasts to generate interferon-inducible protein 10 (IP-10) and monokine induced by IFN- γ (Mig), two

antiangiogenic chemokines (104). In the study, IFN- gene-transferred tumor cells in tumor-bearing mice inhibited tumorigenicity and metastasis of lung cancer (105).

4. MSCs as a viable cancer gene therapy vector

Adult stem cells (ASCs) have the potential to be a major resource in the field of regenerative medicine. They divide into three types of stem cells: neural stem cells (NSCs) (ectoderm), hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs) (mesoderm), and mesodermal stem cells (MSCs) (mesoderm) (106). MSCs can also develop into osteoblasts, chondrocytes, and adipocytes, among other mesodermal lineages (107). Using MSCs as vectors for anti-cancer cytokine delivery has emerged as one of the most important aspects of cancer treatment. MSCs are multipotent mature cells that may be extracted from a variety of sources, including adipose tissue, bone marrow, tooth pulp, umbilical cord blood, and peripheral blood (108, 109). They can also keep their properties for a very long time. MSCs are largely non-immunogenic compared to other cell therapies, which eliminates the risk of immunological rejection (110). Other distinctive qualities of MSCs include the lack of MHC II and its co-stimulatory molecules (CD80, CD86, and CD40), which lower the likelihood of graft against host rejection by avoiding immunological response (111, 112). MSCs have a broad immunosuppressive function and are a purportedly successful therapy for GVHD, according to this characteristic. Clinical investigations have shown that systemic infusions of culture-expanded allogeneic human BM-MSCs for the treatment of steroid-refractory AGVHD patients are effective (111).

MSCs suppress the activation and proliferation of activated T-cells triggered by a range of stimuli, as well as the production of inflammatory cytokines such as TNF-, IL2R-a, elafin, and IFN- (113). Dander et al. evaluated the impact of MSC infusion on lymphocyte counts in transplanted patients with steroid-refractory GVHD for the first time in terms of these features. Surprisingly, after MSC injection, CD4+ T-cell subsets shifted dramatically. In patients whose symptoms improved, Tregs rose, but Th1 and Th17 populations fell dramatically (114).

Furthermore, these cells are simple to control and express a lot of foreign proteins (115). According to research, these cells can be transfected with a high yield; for example, human umbilical cord blood-derived MSC (hUCB-MSCs) can be infected by the lentivector with an efficiency of more than 80.0 percent (116).

The capacity of transplanted MSCs to survive in the tumor microenvironment has increased their use beyond tumor therapy. MSC migration to the tumor site has also been linked to the tumor producing a chemotactic protein (MCP-1). With the expression of chemokine and growth factor receptors such as stromal cell-derived factor 1 (SDF1), monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 (MCP-1), hepatocyte growth factor (HGF), IL-8, neurotrophin-3 (NT-3), transforming growth factor-beta (TGF-), and vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), MSCs have a strong affinity for tumors (VEGF). Furthermore, it is commonly known that the tumor cell-secreted chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 12 (CXCL12) binds to the C-X-C chemokine receptor type 4 (CXCR4), which is expressed primarily in MSCs, leading to MSC tropism and migration (117, 118). When these cells were delivered through the circulation, tumor extravasation ensued (119). These encouraging findings have cleared the road for MSCs to be used as a cancer treatment cytotherapeutic-based vector. Non-engineered MSCs, such as hUCB-MSCs, were found to strongly suppress the proliferation of breast cancer stem cells (CSCs) in vitro and in vivo by Ma et al (120). Cell cycle arrest,

induction of tumor cell death, and reduced activity of Phosphoinositide 3-kinases (PI3Ks) and protein kinase B (PKB, Akt) protein kinases are thought to be involved (120, 121). However, several studies have found that naive MSCs may both promote and inhibit tumor growth, suggesting that they may have bidirectional effects on malignancies. Several preclinical cancer models have described the use of genetically altered MSCs as a vehicle to transfer biological agents to tumor sites. Obviously, MSCs are modified to express cytokines, antiangiogenic agents, prodrug-converting enzymes, and proapoptotic factors (122). Colon cancer (123), pancreatic cancer (124), lung cancer (125), breast carcinoma (126), ovarian cancer (127), prostate cancer (128), hepatocellular carcinoma (129), glioma (130), melanoma (131), and lymphoma (132) have all been treated using these modified cells. Engineered MSCs are used to express a variety of therapeutic molecules against cancer targets, resulting in cancer therapies for a variety of diseases. Anti-angiogenic, cytotoxic, growth factor antagonist, pro-apoptotic, and immunostimulatory drugs are among them. The role of MSCs as a vehicle in cancer immunotherapy is discussed in the following sections.

5. Exosomes generated from MSCs can be used to treat cancer.

Exosomes are nano-sized (40–200 nm) vesicles released by a variety of cell types and found in a variety of bodily fluids. Exosomes generated from MSCs were initially studied in a rat model of cardiac ischemia/reperfusion damage in 2010. MSCs have been shown to generate more exosomes than other cells in tests. Exosomes transport a large number of bioactive molecules, including mRNAs, microRNAs (miRNAs), long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs), genomic DNA, lipids, and proteins. MSCs secrete miRNAs and proteins in exosomes, which have been shown to have biological impacts on other cells in studies. MSC-derived exosomes have been shown to up- or down-regulate transcriptional regulatory genes in cancer cells in recent research (134, 135). MSCs and MSC-derived exosomes have opposing effects on tumor growth because they can either promote or prevent tumor development. It varies depending on the circumstances, tumor kind, growth stage, and MSC concentration (136). In animal models of breast cancer *in vitro* and *in vivo*, Mir-16, a miRNA abundant in MSC-derived exosomes, reduces tumor development and angiogenesis by down-regulating the production of VEGF (137). Exosome composition, on the other hand, may be altered for therapeutic reasons by using cell transfection to introduce proteins and nucleic acids into exosomes. Synthetic double-stranded miR-143, for example, was injected into MSCs and then released into encapsulated exosomes, which were then transported to osteosarcoma cells. *In vitro*, the administration of exosome-formed miR-143 dramatically inhibited osteosarcoma cell migration (138).

Despite a significant body of evidence demonstrating exosomes' ability to regulate immunological processes, clinical data on stem cell-derived immunoregulatory exosomes is limited. MSCs, on the other hand, have been demonstrated to recruit and regulate T lymphocytes in both a cell-to-cell and a paracrine way (106). In other words, these nanoparticles may have inflammatory or antiinflammatory effects on the cells they are introduced to. Overall, it has been postulated that exosomes are good vehicles for cancer immunotherapy because of their ability to alter MSC composition.

In cancer immunotherapy, MSCs can be used as a vehicle for cytokine genes.

The use of immunostimulatory cytokines for cancer therapy has a number of disadvantages. On the one hand, tumor sites are difficult to reach and cytokine half-lives are short, while injection of high quantities of free cytokines appears to be a need for tumor eradication, which leads to greater toxicity and negative side effects (132). As a result, carefully focused

cytokine administration by genetically altered MSCs would be a better option with fewer negative side effects.

MSCs have been reengineered into therapeutic cells using a large number of genes that code for cytokines. Engineered MSCs are designed to release cytokines that can boost pro-tumorigenic immunity in non-inflammatory "silent" settings (139). Engineered MSCs work largely by speeding up tumor infiltration by antitumor immune cells (e.g., natural killer cells and CD4+ and CD8+ T cells) (140, 141), as well as inducing death in malignant cells (142). MSCs that have been cytokine-modified have a lot of potential as an integrated treatment approach for advanced solid tumors (107). The various characteristics of MSCs are closely connected to the relevant molecular repressive modes of action of cytokine-engineered MSCs inside tumor microenvironments. First and foremost, the chances of these immunoprivileged cells being rejected are quite slim. A considerable positive tropism toward tumor proximity is their second favorable feature. These are suitable for migrating to the same homing location as migrating cancer stem cells (107). Ex vivo-transduced MSC engraftment was found at the site of glioma, colon, breast, ovarian, and melanoma lung metastasis tumors in animal models (143,144,145).

The increasing tumor microenvironment can cause cytokine-engineered MSCs to develop specifically into stromal cells at tumor locations and thereafter integrate into the tumor architecture, but this does not happen in normal tissues (146). These cells have already been committed to producing pro-inflammatory cytokines and inhibiting Akt activation in cancer cells and tumor microvascular endothelium. Until now, no other sort of cell vehicle has been able to match these characteristics (107). Furthermore, because of their hypoimmunogenic features, the target-specific therapeutic expression of cytokine-engineered MSCs delivers prolonged anticancer effects (up to 6 months) without long-term overt damage to the host body (107). Multiple preclinical and clinical investigations have revealed successful ex vivo transduction of MSCs using various viral vectors such as retroviral, lentiviral, and adenoviral, resulting in the most promising treatment platform against various malignancies (147). MSCs were soon used for cytokine gene therapy in a variety of malignancies, including glioma (148), pancreatic (149), renal (147), breast malignancies (107), and sarcoma (150).

Interferons are proteins that have a role in the immune system (IFNs).

Studený et al. published a seminal paper in 2002 that described the use of MSCs with forced production of certain cytokines for the treatment of solid malignancies. Compared to the healthy control group, IFN-transduced MSCs inhibited the formation of melanoma malignant cells in vivo and enhanced mouse survival (twice) (131). In a mouse melanoma model, considerable tumor elimination was achieved when syngeneic MSCs expressing IFN- were used to treat the tumor. MSCs were shown to be dispersed within the tumor and emitted a considerable amount of IFN- in situ for the first time (151). Wang et al. systemically administered IFN-expressing MSCs to mice with prostate xenografts and found a significant reduction in tumor size and weight, as well as improved animal survival, when compared to controls (152).

The same outcomes were obtained in a bladder tumor mouse model (153). Furthermore, in mice with pre-existing metastases of melanoma, breast, prostate, and hepatoma cancers, IFN-IL-12 expressing MSC treatment significantly slowed the spread of metastases into multistep lymph nodes (LN) and internal organs (149, 154). In addition, systemic treatment of MSC that expresses IFN- reduced the proliferation of B16F10 melanoma cells and significantly

increased survival. Immunohistochemistry examination of MSC-IFN-treated animals' lungs revealed enhanced tumor cell death and decreased blood vessel numbers (151). In 2011, a similar study looked at the therapeutic effect of MSC producing cells against cancerous plasma cells. The MSC-IFN- substantially slowed tumor development in vivo and extended the mice's overall life after subcutaneous injection in a mouse plasmacytoma model (155).

Interleukins

In a syngeneic mouse melanoma model, treatment of glioma with human MSC that expresses IL-2 resulted in a significant decrease in tumor mass and improved participant survival (156). Injection of genetically engineered IL-2-expressing MSC into an ovarian cancer mouse model resulted in apoptosis, according to You et al. (157). Not unexpectedly, IL-12-secreting MSCs have been demonstrated to inhibit metastasis and promote cancer cell death in melanoma, lung cancer, and hepatoma-bearing mice with 75, 83, and 91 percent effectiveness, respectively (157). In addition, systemic injection of modified cells greatly slowed the progression of metastasis in mid- and late-stage tumors while causing minimal damage. Another study found that injecting human bone marrow MSCs (hBM-MSCs) modified with murine IL-12 inhibited the development of renal cell carcinoma in a mouse xenograft model by increasing INF- levels, indicating that IFN- plays a key role in tumor regression. NK cells appear to play a role in the anti-tumor effect of hBM-MSC/mIL-12 (147). Ewing's sarcoma and head-and-neck tumors have also been suppressed using murine BM-MSCs/mIL-12 (75, 150). The ovarian cancer model was used to test the hUC-MSCs/IL-12 combination. In vitro and in vivo, the supernatant of IL-12-engineered hUC-MSCs was able to significantly lower cell proliferation and limit malignant cell growth (158). Similarly, when murine BM-MSCs were retrovirally modified to express IL-12 and injected subcutaneously in syngeneic and allogeneic breast cancer models, they markedly slowed tumor development (159). Interleukin-15 (IL-15), another interleukin with anticancer efficacy in several animal models and human clinical trials (160), functions similarly to IL-2 but does not trigger the proliferation of regulatory T cells (Treg). In mice with pancreatic tumors, hUCB-MSCs transduced with the murine IL-15 gene were shown to be able to localize to the tumor site, where the release of IL-15 antitumor activity was increased by both NK and CD8+ T lymphocytes, and tumor development was inhibited (161). In recent research, it was shown that transplanting IL-21-secreting hUCB-MSCs to mice carrying ovarian cancer xenografts increased NK cell cytotoxicity and IFN-, IL-4, and TNF- levels (162). MSCs/IL-21 have also been studied in the treatment of B-cell lymphoma; when administered intravenously, MSCs/IL-21 showed a powerful antitumor impact and was linked to enhanced survival through increased NK and effector T cell activity (132).

The effects of IL-18 administration via MSCs as a treatment method for gliomas were studied by Xu et al. In mice with noninvasive and invasive gliomas, MSCs modified to produce secretable IL-18 were demonstrated to suppress the development of malignant cells by increasing T cell infiltration and long-term antitumor immunity, as well as improving survival (163). With IFN-, the effectiveness of IL-18 was increased. Rat bone marrow MSCs (rBM-MSCs) were transduced with a bicistronic lentiviral vector containing the genes for IL-18 and IFN-. Interestingly, glioma cell regression was boosted, suggesting that IL-18 and IFN- work in concert against tumor cells (164). In vitro experiments revealed that hUC-MSCs/IL-18 significantly reduced breast cancer cell growth and invasion (165, 166). In a recent study, the antitumoral activity of Interleukin-28 (IL-28) was demonstrated in a human esophageal cancer or colon cancer mouse model. The antiproliferative and antiangiogenesis effects of hBM-MSCs/IL-28A were observed (167). hUCB-derived MSC were effectively used as carriers for

delivering IL-24 to help treat lung cancer cells by inducing apoptosis and cell cycle arrest in a 2013 research. Both in vitro and in vivo, these cells have antiangiogenic properties (168). In a transplant tumor model, Hombach and colleagues recently showed that altered MSCs releasing IL7 and IL12 were better than non-modified MSCs in promoting the CAR T cell response and improving anti-tumor activity (169).

TNF-, a key cytokine in the early immune response, has been utilized to transduce MSCs with CD40 ligand (CD40L) (170). Through inducing a proinflammatory response and encouraging a T helper 2 (Th2) to T helper 1 (Th1) shift, MSCs/TNF-/CD40L displayed anti-proliferative effects in animal models of human breast cancer.

6. Conclusion

These discoveries, taken together, establish modified MSCs as a new study topic for cancer therapy. Future cancer patients will benefit greatly from their use. MSCs have excellent tumor-directed migratory and integration capabilities, making them suitable carriers for delivering anticancer drugs, particularly cytokines. They've been in use in the clinic for around ten years. MSCs have been used to achieve effective cancer therapy in everything from animal models to clinical trials.

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